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The Effect of External Debt on The Economic Growth of Ghana

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ABSTRACT

This article investigates the relationship between external debt and Ghana's economic growth using multiple regression analysis with data spanning from 1983 to 2019. Various experimental tests were used to confirm the primary hypothesis in the multiple regression analysis (OLS model). Augmented Dickey fuller test to check for the variables' stationarity. CUSUM test was used to check the residual stability of the model. Granger causality test and the Johansen co-integration test revealed short run causal effect and long run relationship respectively between the dependent variable (GDP) and the independent variable (External debt). The OLS regression results revealed that external debt has significant negative impact on the economy of Ghana. The substantial adverse impact may be linked to Ghana's weak macroeconomic framework, as well as improperly managed sectors with government bureaucracy and a high level of corruption among government officials. The study recommends that, external debt should be used for the reason for which it was acquired, which is infrastructural development to help enhance the business setting and productive capacity, thereby making repayment easier and also lessen the need of foreign loans to support government programmes.

Keywords

Ghana, External Debt, Economic Growth, Export, GDP, Multiple Regression, OLS Model

1. Introduction

The paramount goal of most developing countries is to mobilize resources from various sources and invest them into developmental projects that will foster economic growth. It is the primary concern of all countries, especially less developed countries (LDCs) facing growing fiscal deficits to achieve sustainable economic growth. One of the many ways these countries (LDCs) seek to achieve that is by borrowing money from external sources such as World bank and International Monetary Fund (IMF). There is plethora of papers that have analysed the impact external debt have on economic growth. In the 1980s, Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), which Ghana happens to be a part of, experienced excruciating external debt crisis, which in turn invited the

intervention of the World Bank and International Monetary Fund (IMF), via the Highly Indebted Poor Countries (HIPC) program (1). The program was initiated in 1996, with the aim of providing aids to struggling nations like Ghana to subdue unsustainable high levels of external debt. It was crafted with the fundamental aim of granting debt relief and rescuing the developing countries from the hardship of repaying their huge debt. The underlying condition for debt relief was that these SSA countries had to implement significant economic reforms and poverty reduction strategies. Ghana had met these requirements and had its external debts waived by 2005. Ghana didn't hesitate to go back to its massive external borrowing ways shortly after its debt burden was lifted. This was and continues to be due to the comparatively low interest rate on foreign loans as compared to domestic loans' interest rates. The total external debt of Ghana as of 2019 was \$26.74 billion which is about 39 percent of total GDP (2).

Economists and financial analysts are concerned about the long-term effects of external debt on the economy. Some empirical studies tried to focus on the trend, but such researches were only fixated on the salient roots of external borrowing, overlooking the latent threat it poses for the growth of the economy. The primary focus of this research is to find out how external debt affects Ghana's economic growth. A multiple regression model is used to analyze the effect of various economic variables on economic growth based on data covering the period 1983 to 2019.

2. Literature Review

2.1 External Debt and Its Components

External debt is made up of debts issued by foreign lenders including international financial institutions, international markets, commercial banks, and governments. External debt is a type of financial capital (3). Developing countries often need external debt to facilitate development and economic stability. The reasons for the external debt of developing countries are; to be guided by social policies, to eliminate foreign exchange imbalances caused by economic policies, to eliminate insufficient income caused by fiscal policies, and the influence of external factors related to the external situation (4). In heavily indebted countries with insufficient resources and low capital accumulation, economic growth and poverty have become fundamental problems along with the inability to repay debt due to high debt (5). In these countries, high debt rates lead to low production levels, and the imbalance in the levels of saving, investment and production has a negative impact on economic development, making it difficult to get out of the poverty rabbit hole (6).

Figure 1 External Debt and Its Components

Source: [World Bank, 2020](#)

Figure 1 illustrates the external debt and its components. Short term and long-term debt as well as the amount of IMF credits, constitute total external debt. Non-guaranteed private sector external debts, public sector external debts, and public guaranteed external debts are the three types of external debts categorised with respect to debtors. Official creditors (multilateral and bilateral) and private creditors (commercial banks, bonds, and others) are the two classes of creditors (lenders) when it comes to external debts (7).

2.2 Empirical Positive Effects of External Debts on Economic Growth

[Owusu-Nantwi & Christopher Erickson \(2016\), \(8\)](#) explored the long-term and causal link between public debt and economic development in Ghana using Johansen cointegration and the vector error correction model. From 1970 to 2012, annual time series data from the World Bank Development Indicators and the IMF Economic Outlook were compiled. Their research discovered a long-run positive and statistically significant connection between public debt and economic growth. They also claimed that there is a bidirectional Granger causation relationship between public debt and economic development in the short run. According to the research, Ghana should use public debt to fund high-priority projects and initiatives that are well-received and self-sustaining and can contribute to economic growth.

Bangladesh has relied significantly on public debt to finance its budget and balance of payment deficits since independence (9). His research looked at how Bangladesh's public debt affects the country's economic growth. Two models, the Investment model and the Growth model, were employed in their research for this aim. The

investment model was used to look at the indirect effect of public debt on economic development by looking at its impact on investment. The direct link between public debt and economic growth was investigated in the growth model using data from 1974 to 2014. His projected results revealed a positive relationship between public debt and both investment and economic development. His empirical findings also showed that government debt has an indirect positive effect on growth through encouraging investment. [Spilioti \(2015\), \(10\)](#) investigated the average effect of government debt on GDP growth in the Euro area countries. The empirical results proposed that the effect of debt on economic growth is positive and statistically highly significant.

[Mohanty & Mishra \(2016\), \(11\)](#) also examined the effect of public debt on economic growth of 14 major (non-special category) States in India by using both Dynamic Ordinary Least Square (DOLS) and Fully-Modified Ordinary Least Square (FMOLS) methods. Their findings from both methods suggested positive and statistically significant impact of public external debt on economic growth.

2.3 Empirical Negative Effects of External Debts on Economic Growth

The impact of external public debt on economic growth in four East African nations was investigated by [\(12\)](#). Kenya, Tanzania, Uganda, and Rwanda were the countries selected for their study. Using fixed effect and random effects model estimate approaches, they looked into the dangers and costs associated with public debt in various nations. According to their results, external debt has a detrimental effect or influence on economic growth in East African countries. In a similar vein, [Dey & Tareque \(2020\), \(13\)](#) looked at the influence of external debt on Bangladesh's economic development in the context of a wider macroeconomic scenario. They used the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) bounds testing technique to cointegration to examine empirical cointegration, long-run and short-run dynamics of the relevant variables. Their findings indicated that foreign debt has a detrimental influence on economic growth.

[Anderu et al., \(2019\), \(14\)](#) investigated the link between external debt and Nigerian economic development from 1980 to 2016. The researchers used the Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) method using descriptive statistics. Their findings revealed that Nigeria's foreign debt has a substantial negative relationship with and impact on the country's economic growth. They concluded that, Nigerian external debt does not promote economic growth. [Atinafu \(2020\), \(15\)](#) endeavored to estimate the impact of Ethiopia's public foreign debt on economic development. They used the Auto Regressive Distributive Lag model to achieve so (ARDL modeling). His empirical findings indicated that a high stock of public external debt has a substantial negative effect or influence on economic growth and presents significant problems to the economy in the long run.

[Ehigiamusoe & Lean \(2020\), \(16\)](#) in their study scrutinized the effect of debt and deficit on the finance–growth nexus in West Africa. According to their findings, the influence of financial development on economic growth differs depending on debt and deficit levels. When debt and deficit surpass threshold levels of 48.6% and -

13.5 percent of GDP, respectively, the marginal impacts of financial development on growth turn negative. According to their findings, the financial sector is one of the channels through which debt and deficit have an impact on economic development. Thus, a rise in financial development would not yield the required long-run economic benefits lest it is accompanied by a decrease in government debt and fiscal deficit. According to (17), external debt has yoked the evolutionary potential of a country. A panel data of countries from 1970 to 2010 unveiled a negative or an adverse and robust effect of public external debt on economic growth. (18) investigated the relationship between external debt and economic development in Nigeria. Between 1994 and 2008, he used the Ordinary Least Squares Method (OLS), Error Correction, and parsimonious models to analyze quarterly data. According to his research, debt has a detrimental influence on economic growth.

Boboye & Ojo (2012), (19) investigated the impact of Nigeria's foreign debt burden on the country's economic growth and development. They used the OLS regression analysis. External debt load has a negative impact on the nation's income and per capita income, according to the findings. The high amount of foreign debt resulted in the depreciation of the national currency, an increase in worker retrenchment, a constant strike, and a substandard educational system. Nigeria's economy suffered as a result of this. (20) in their paper, investigated the influence of government debt on Ghana's economic growth. With data covering the years 1990 to 2015, they utilized the Ordinary Least Squares method. They tested three linked models at the domestic and external levels, including the overall expansion of the Ghanaian economy, to see how government debt (both external and domestic) affected the economy. Their studies indicated that debt (both domestic and external) had a negative connection with growth in Ghana's economy, and they propose, among other things, that government debt borrowing be avoided while revenue growth through tax reform programs be promoted. (21) examined Kenya's external debt structure and its consequences on economic growth. According to the conclusions of her research, Kenya's external debt is primarily official, with a larger share coming from multilateral sources. The empirical results, which were based on time series data from 1970 to 1995, showed that foreign debt buildup had a detrimental influence on economic growth and private investment.

3. Methodology

The prime econometric model employed in the research is the ordinary least squares regression model. World Bank (22), was the main source of data for variables. The data used in this study covers the period 1983 to 2019 (37 years). GDP was used as the dependent variable and regressed with External debt, Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), Exports, Official Development Assistance & Official Aid (ODA) and Gross Fixed Capital Formation (GFCF).

The equation was formulated as:

$$Y_t = mX + b + \mu$$

where:

Y_t : Dependent variable

X_t : Independent variable

b: Constant term

t: Time trend

μ : is the random error term, which is the difference between the actual value of a dependent variable and its predicted value

Econometrically, the model for this research analysis will be stated as;

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \mu$$

where Y_t is known as the Dependent variable, β_0 is known as the Intercept while β_1, β_2, \dots and β_5 are known as the Coefficients.

Thus;

$$Y = GDP_t$$

The model for estimating the impact of external debt on economic growth of Ghana is expressed as;

$$GDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 EXD + \beta_2 EXP + \beta_3 GFCF + \beta_4 FDI + \beta_5 ODA + \mu \dots \dots (eqn1)$$

Where;

GDP represent Economic Growth of Ghana,

EXD – Represents External debt

EXP – Represents Exports

GFCF – Represents Gross Fixed Capital Formation,

FDI – Represents Foreign Direct Investments

ODA – Grants, excluding technical cooperation

μ – Random error term

The log form of the model can be expressed as follows:

$$\text{LogGDP} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LogEXD} + \beta_2 \text{LogEXP} + \beta_3 \text{LogGFCF} + \beta_4 \text{LogFDI} + \beta_5 \text{LogODA} + \mu \dots (eqn2)$$

Table 1 Selected Variables, Their Descriptions and Their Expected Signs

Variables	Descriptions of Variables	Expected Signs
Gross Domestic Product (GDP)	The total amount of all monetary or market values accumulated inside a country's boundaries through the production of products and supply of services at a specific time, generally within a year, is known as Gross Domestic Product.	+/-
Export	The total number of products and services produced in a domestic country and sold to consumers in another country is referred to as exports.	+/-
Foreign Direct Investment (FDI)	The direct flow of equity investment from an external firm, organisation, or individual into another nation is known as foreign direct investment. It involves the summation of reinvested revenue, equity capital and other related capital.	+/-
Gross Fixed Capital Formation (GFCF)	The European System of Accounts (ESA) defines gross fixed capital formation as the acquisitions, minus disposals, of fixed assets by resident producers over a given period, plus certain additions to the value of non-produced assets realised by producer or institutional units' productive activity.	+/-
Official Development Assistance & Official Aid (ODA)	Official development assistance (ODA) is defined as government aid designed to promote the economic development and welfare of developing countries. Aid may be provided bilaterally, from donor to recipient, or channeled through a multilateral development agency such as the United Nations or the World Bank, (23).	+/-

Source: Author's Compilation, 2022

4. Data Analysis and Presentation of Results

4.1 Introduction

The ordinary least squares (OLS) statistical analysis approach is used to estimate the unknown parameters in the econometric model. A multiple econometric model was used to achieve this goal, using 5 independent variables (external debt, foreign direct investment, exports, ODA, and gross fixed capital formation) with one dependent variable (Gross domestic product). This section also covers model definition, data processing, and model estimate using World Bank data for variables from 1983 to 2019.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

Table 2, shows the descriptive statistics of the data used in this study, from 1983 to 2019. The table shows the Mean, Median, Maximum, Minimum and Standard deviation of each variable with respect to the study period. The table also contains key values/outputs such as the Skewness Kurtosis, Jarque-Berra and its respective Probabilities, the Sum and their Sum sq. Dev.

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics of Variables for Ghana (1983-2019)

	GDP	EXD	EXP	GFCF	FDI	ODA
Mean	2.10E+10	8.54E+09	6.50E+09	4.18E+09	1.12E+09	9.14E+08
Median	7.48E+09	6.61E+09	2.53E+09	1.64E+09	1.45E+08	7.16E+08
Maximum	6.83E+10	2.67E+10	2.56E+10	1.51E+10	3.88E+09	1.80E+09
Minimum	4.06E+09	1.67E+09	2.25E+08	1.53E+08	2000000	1.08E+08
Std. Dev.	2.17E+10	6.66E+09	7.34E+09	4.86E+09	1.45E+09	4.72E+08
Skewness	1.071068	1.373951	1.175246	1.316366	0.763415	0.354413
Kurtosis	2.600957	3.711146	3.01267	3.159147	1.741551	2.16517
Jarque-Bera	7.319808	12.42074	8.517672	10.72476	6.035481	1.849037
Probability	0.025735	0.002008	0.014139	0.00469	0.048912	0.396722
Sum	7.76E+11	3.16E+11	2.41E+11	1.55E+11	4.15E+10	3.38E+10
Sum Sq. Dev.	1.69E+22	1.60E+21	1.94E+21	8.49E+20	7.55E+19	8.02E+18
Observations	37	37	37	37	37	37

Source: Author's Computations using Eviews10, 2022

4.3 Unit Root Test

The Augmented Dickey Fuller unit root test was used to determine the variables' stationarity. For levels and 1st differencing, critical value was set at 5%. The critical number remained unchanged at (-3.5). The Schwarz Information Criterion with a maximum of two lags was used to perform the unit root test. The t-statistical value is expected to be greater than (-3.5) to deem each variable stationary with the critical value set at (-3.5). As a result, when either the t-statistical value or both values are less than the critical value, a variable (GDP) is termed non stationary (-3.5).

Table 3 Augmented Dickey Fuller Results

Variables	ADF Stat	Prob.	5% Critical Value	Order of Integration	Assessment
LogGDP	-5.175964	0.0002	-2.943427	I (1)	Stationary
LogEXD	-5.004251	0.0002	-2.943427	I (1)	Stationary
LogEXP	-4.569603	0.0008	-2.943427	I (1)	Stationary
LogGFCF	-6.486061	0.0000	-3.536601	I (1)	Stationary
LogFDI	-5.601776	0.0000	-2.943427	I (1)	Stationary
LogODA	-7.913579	0.0000	-2.945842	I (1)	Stationary

Source: Author Computation Using E-views 10, 2022

Unit Root Test Summary: It can be observed that all variables selected for this research become stationary at 1st differencing. In the absence of non-stationaries, the research proceeds to perform the cointegration test to check for long-run relationships between the time series variables before proceeding to proper estimations.

4.4 Lag Length Selection Criteria

According to Banerjee et al., 1993 choosing an optimal lag length is very significant because selecting too few lags may gravely affect the size of the test by over-rejecting the null hypothesis when it is true. On the other hand, using too many lags may reduce the power or credibility of the test by truncating the degree of freedom (24). In choosing lag length for the unrestricted VAR model, 5 different lag selection criteria were employed and the result is shown in Table 4.

Table 4 VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

Endogenous variables: GDP EXD EXP GFCF FDI ODA

Exogenous variables: C

Sample: 1983 2019

Included observations: 35

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-4707.351	NA	3.8e+109	269.3344	269.6010	269.4264
1	-4531.777	280.9183	1.3e+106	261.3587	263.2251*	262.0030
2	-4471.682	75.54814*	4.1e+105*	259.9818*	263.4480	261.1784*

* indicates lag order selected by the criterion

LR: sequential modified LR test statistic (each test at 5% level)

FPE: Final prediction error

AIC: Akaike information criterion

SC: Schwarz information criterion

HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion

Source: Author's Computations using Eviews10, 2022

The lesser the likelihood-ratios, Akaike Information Criterion, Schwarz Information Criterion values or figures the better. The result from table 4 above shows the lag(s) that the various lag selection criteria chose as their respective optimal lag.

4.5 Cointegration Test

The cointegration test procedure is executed in order to ascertain a long-run relationship between the study variables. According to Gujarati, 2004, if two variables have a long-run or an equilibrium relationship between them, they are considered to be cointegrated (25). The renowned Johansen cointegration test will be used in this study to test for cointegration among the variables.

Performing Johansen Cointegration Test

In defining the fitting lags for the model, a lag length criterion is specified. Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) is selected to determine or check the consistency of the model, hence lag 2 becomes the optimal lag. After that, Johansen Cointegration Test is performed with GDP as the normalization variable.

The Johansen Cointegration Test Results

The results of the Johansen cointegration test are shown in the table below. There are four cointegration equations with statistical trace values above the critical values of 5% and probability values below 1%, according to the trace findings. As a result, the null hypothesis that the variables do not have co-integration is rejected. Since there are three cointegration equations with statistical values above the critical values of 5% and probability values below 1%, the findings of the Maximum Eigen justify dismissal of the null hypothesis.

Table 5 Trace and Max-Eigen Results

Sample (adjusted): 1986 2019

Included observations: 34 after adjustments

Trend assumption: Linear deterministic trend

Series: GDP EXD EXP GFCF FDI ODA

Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 2

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
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None *	0.940370	229.8484	95.75366	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.835781	133.9820	69.81889	0.0000
At most 2 *	0.712897	72.55906	47.85613	0.0001
At most 3 *	0.405641	30.12995	29.79707	0.0458
At most 4	0.290414	12.44068	15.49471	0.1370
At most 5	0.022570	0.776164	3.841466	0.3783

Trace test indicates 4 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.940370	95.86638	40.07757	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.835781	61.42292	33.87687	0.0000
At most 2 *	0.712897	42.42911	27.58434	0.0003
At most 3	0.405641	17.68927	21.13162	0.1419
At most 4	0.290414	11.66452	14.26460	0.1239
At most 5	0.022570	0.776164	3.841466	0.3783

Max-eigenvalue test indicates 3 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Source: Author's Computations using Eviews10, 2022

Conclusion: The null hypothesis of no cointegration is rejected in the model with respect to the alternative of a cointegration relationship. Thus, there is long-run relationship between the dependent and the independent variables. This also affirms that the original regression is cleared of spuriousness.

4.6 Regression Results Analysis

In the table below, an ordinary least squares model was used to examine the relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables used. Gross Domestic Product (GDP) was employed as the dependent variable in this multiple regression, with External debt (EXD), Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), Exports (EXP), Official Development Assistance & Official Aid (ODA), and Gross Fixed Capital Formation (GFCF) as the independent variables. Ordinary Least Squared was used in running the regression.

Table 6 Regression Results

Dependent Variable: GDP

Method: Least Squares

Sample: 1983 2019

Included observations: 37

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
EXD	-0.795532	0.203510	-3.909055	0.0005
EXP	2.094128	0.273993	7.643012	0.0000
GFCF	1.946426	0.205329	9.479551	0.0000
FDI	2.131021	0.974668	2.186406	0.0365
ODA	-2.526311	1.088145	-2.321667	0.0270
C	5.92E+09	1.05E+09	5.654111	0.0000
R-squared	0.993061	Mean dependent var		2.10E+10
Adjusted R-squared	0.991942	S.D. dependent var		2.17E+10
S.E. of regression	1.94E+09	Akaike info criterion		45.76218
Sum squared resid	1.17E+20	Schwarz criterion		46.02341
Log likelihood	-840.6003	Hannan-Quinn criter.		45.85428
F-statistic	887.3559	Durbin-Watson stat		2.030694
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Author's Computations using Eviews10, 2022

$$Y (\text{GDP}) = 5920841254.86 - 0.795532 * X_1 + 2.094128 * X_2 + 1.946426 * X_3 + 2.131021 * X_4 - 2.526311 * X_5$$

From the regression result in table 6 the prob values of all independent variable are lesser than 5%. Therefore, it can be said that the independent variables of the model have significant influence on the dependent variable. The model can be said to be fit since the Adjusted R-squared is 0.991942, thus, the independent variables cumulatively explain 99.19% of the dependent variable. Durbin-Watson stat. value of 2.030694 proves that the model is free from autocorrelation. Prob(F-statistic) value is 0.000000 (less than 5%), signifying that the combine effect of all independent variables on dependent variable is highly significant.

The Impact of External Debt on Ghana's Economic Growth

The regression result in Table 6 shows that the coefficient of external debt is negative (-0.795532) which confirms to prior expectation that there is a negative relationship between Ghana's economic growth and external debt. It can be concluded that one unit increase in the external debt on average, ceteris paribus, can decrease Ghana's gross domestic product by -0.795532. A lower prob. value of 0.0005 which is less than 0.5% implies that the variable is significant. The substantial adverse impact may be linked to Ghana's weak macroeconomic framework, as well as improperly managed sectors with government bureaucracy and a high level of corruption among government officials. This result is consistent with the research findings of (12), (18) and (19) which revealed a significant negative impact of external debt on Ghana's economic growth. . In line with the findings of (14), this study suggests that external debts should be used to boost productivity in an efficient manner and entreat policy makers to center long term policy towards the disbursement of the loans in attempt to solve short and long run socioeconomic challenges.

The Impact of Export on Ghana's Economic Growth

The regression result in Table 6 shows that the coefficient of external debt is positive (2.094128) which is consistent with the findings of (26) and (27). Per the regression result, it can be said that one unit increase in the external debt on average, all things being equal, leads to an increase in Ghana's gross domestic product by 2.094128. A lower prob. value of 0.0000 which is less than 0.5% implies that the variable is significant. The study implores Ghanaian government to put in more efforts to diversify the economy and further encourage more export-oriented firms after examining and refining their current incentive structures. The fundamental assumption is that the more resources are allocated to the sector and more effective policies are put in place to support it flourish, the more export will bolster the country's GDP.

The Impact of Gross Fixed Capital Formation on Ghana's Economic Growth

From Table 6, the coefficient of Gross Fixed Capital Formation is positive; 1.946426, which imply that there is a positive relationship between Ghana's economic growth and GFCF. The study's result resonates with the findings of (28) and (29). It can be concluded that one unit increase in the importation of goods and services can on the average increase Ghana's gross domestic product by 1.946426. A lower prob value of 0.0000 which is less than 0.5% implies that the variable is significant. The government of Ghana should make conscious effort to facilitate the increase in the level of capital formation since it has the potential to drive the economy to unprecedented growth.

The Impact of Foreign Direct Investment on Ghana's Economic Growth

The coefficient of FDI in table 6 is positive; 2.131021 which imply that there is a positive relationship between Ghana's economic growth and FDI. The study's result resonates with the findings of (30) and (31). It can be concluded that one unit increase in FDI can on the average, *ceteris paribus*, increase Ghana's gross domestic product by 2.131021. A lower prob value of 0.0365 which is less than 0.5% implies that the variable is significant. The study proposes that the government restructure Ghana's foreign sector so that all trade barriers, such as arbitrary tariffs, import and export charges, and other levies, be lowered in order to entice investors.

The Impact of Official Development Assistance & Official Aid on Ghana's Economic Growth (ODA)

The statistical analysis in the model used shows that ODA has a negative impact on the economic growth of Ghana which lends support to the findings of (32) and (33). The coefficient of ODA is -2.526311 thus a negative relationship which implies that an increase in ODA will lead to a decline in Ghana's economic growth and vice versa. A lower probability value of 0.0270 implies that the variable is significant with a standard deviation of 1.088145. The study proposes that if the Ghanaian government strive for bureaucratic quality and effectively manage foreign aid, Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) will be achieved.

Hypothesis Test

H0= There is no significant negative impact of External Debt on Ghana's GDP

H0= There is a significant negative impact of External Debt on Ghana's GDP

The OLS model results in Table 6 revealed the Probability Value for the estimated regression of the lead independent variable to be less than 0.05 percent (i.e., 0.0005). The results obtained in Table 6 suggests that the study rejects the null hypothesis and concludes that there is a significant negative relationship between economic growth and external debt during the period of study.

4.7 Granger Causality Test

The granger causality test is a statistical instrument used in time series analysis to predict the impact of one variable on another, primarily the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. It's used to predict or calculate the rate at which an independent variable can affect or statistically change an independent variable; in other words, how a percentage change in an independent variable leads to a percentage change in the dependent variable. The Chi-sq from the Granger causality test reveals short run causal effects and the decision criteria is to reject the Null hypothesis if the probability value of the Chi-sq is less than or equal to 0.05.

Table 7 VAR Granger Causality/Block Exogeneity Wald Tests

VAR Granger Causality/Block Exogeneity Wald Tests

Sample: 1983 2019

Included observations: 35

Dependent variable: GDP

Excluded	Chi-sq	df	Prob.
EXD	40.23433	2	0.0000
EXP	55.61970	2	0.0000
GFCF	27.56102	2	0.0000
FDI	7.816018	2	0.0201
ODA	5.864940	2	0.0533
All	158.0130	10	0.0000

Source: Author's Computations using Eviews10, 2022

Table 7, shows that the variables; External Debt, Export, GFCF, FDI have a strong causative influence on GDP growth with their Prob values all lesser than 0.05 except ODA which has a Prob value of 0.533. Thus, it can be concluded that except ODA which doesn't have a short run casual on the dependent variable, all the other independent variables do have a short run casual effect on the dependent variable.

4.8 Stability Diagnostics

The results of the stability test employing the CUSUM test, as shown in figure 2, prove the model's stability. The estimations are considered stable over time because the residual plot did not go beyond the 5% significant boundaries.

Figure 2 CUSUM Test

Source: Author's Computations using Eviews10, 2022

Figure 2: A diagram depicting the performance or pattern of the residuals regarding their stability. The residuals would have been considered unstable if the curved line that represents them fell outside the two extreme lines that represent the crucial regions.

5. Conclusion

Official debts, mostly from multilateral sources and in the form of concessional loans, account for a larger share of Ghana's external debt. As a result, the nation has been able to borrow on favourable conditions. Both internal and external factors have contributed to Ghana's external debt. Internal variables include fiscal policies that are too expansionary and trade policies that are extremely skewed, particularly, ones that have a large bias against exports. External factors include declining terms of trade, which led to BOP deficits, rising global interest rates, and growing protectionism by advanced economies, which tended to discriminate against exports from developing countries.

The aim of the study was to assess the impact of the external debt on the economic growth of Ghana using data from 1983 to 2019. The relationship between external debt and economic growth was investigated using multiple regression analysis. Some experimental tests were used to confirm the primary hypothesis in the North American Academic Research, 5(3) | March 2022 | <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6371575> Monthly Journal by TWASP, USA | 134

multiple regression analysis. Augmented Dickey fuller test to check for the variables' stationarity and from the results, all variables were stationary at 1ST Differencing. CUSUM test was used to check the residual stability of the model and the result showed that the estimations are considered stable over time because the residual plot did not go beyond the 5% significant boundaries. Granger causality test indicated short run causal effects while the Johansen co-integration test revealed long run relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables. The OLS results revealed that external debt has significant negative impact on the economy of Ghana. These findings are consistent with the results of (12),(18) and (19). The research also revealed that exports, FDI and GFCF also have significant positive impact on the economy's growth. Findings from the study also showed that ODA has negative impact on economic growth. With the exception of official development assistance and official aid, all other independent variables, namely; external debt, export, gross fixed capital formation, foreign direct investment and have a short run causal effect on GDP.

6. Recommendations

Based on the study's results and conclusions, the following suggestions for policymakers, government agencies, and competent authorities for action were made.

1. External debt should be used for the reason for which it was acquired, which should be fundamental and infrastructural development to help enhance the business setting and productive capacity, thereby making repayment easier.
2. Efforts should be directed on diversifying the economy and government revenue, since this would assist lessen the need of foreign loans to support government programmes.
3. Authorities should develop measures that stimulate foreign investment while reducing demand for imported goods in order to strengthen the Ghana cedi.
4. Increased export profits, anchored by an export-led growth strategy, as well as investment in human capital, should be used to fund development initiatives in Ghana, since these are the best long-term alternatives to external debt.
5. The government should pay greater attention to its debt management profile, notably its expenditure items.
6. Effective macroeconomic management of the economy as at large is essential as it influences the amount and servicing of external debt, as well as the credit rating.

Suggestions for Further Research

External debt is a very intriguing topic that encompasses many subjects; thus, it is essential to investigate some of the following areas in future research: The effect of private external debt on economic development, the effect of external debt on fixed capital formation, and the effect of external debt and public debt overhang on economic growth.

References

1. Edo S, Osadolor NE, Dading IF. Growing external debt and declining export: The concurrent impediments in economic growth of Sub-Saharan African countries. *Int Econ* [Internet]. 2020;161(November 2019):173–87. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inteco.2019.11.013>
2. World Bank IDS. External debt stocks, total (DOD, current US\$) - Ghana [Internet]. The World Bank Group. 2022 [cited 2022 Mar 10]. p. 1. Available from: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/DT.DOD.DECT.CD?locations=GH>
3. YILDIZ F. The impact of external debt on growth: Evidence from highly indebted poor countries (HIPC). *J Policy Model*. 2016;68.
4. Tiruneh MW. External Imbalances As An Explanation for Growth Rate Differences Across Time and Space: An Econometric Exploration. IMU. 2003;
5. Seyidođlu H. *International Economics Theory and Policy and Practice*. 2009;
6. Sachs JD. Resolving the Debt Crisis of Low-Income Countries. *Brookings Inst Press* [Internet]. 2002;33(1):257–86. Available from: <http://muse.jhu.edu/journals/eca/summary/v2002/2002.1sachs.html>
7. World Bank. *International Debt Statistics 2021* [Internet]. 2020 [cited 2021 Aug 23]. Available from: <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/34588>
8. Owusu-nantwi V, Christopher Erickson. *Public Debt and Economic Growth in Ghana*. Blackwell Publ Ltd. 2016;28(1):116–26.
9. Saifuddin M. Public Debt and Economic Growth: Evidence from Bangladesh. *Glob J Manag Bus Res B Econ Commer*. 2016;16(5):1–10.
10. Spilioti S. The relationship between the government debt and GDP growth : evidence of the Euro area countries. *Invest Manag Financ Innov*. 2015;12(1):174–8.
11. Mohanty AR, Mishra BR. Impact of Public Debt on Economic Growth: Evidence from Indian States. *Vilakshan XIMB J Manag* [Internet]. 2016;13(2):1–21. Available from: <http://auth.rtu.lv/php/redirect.php?goto=http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=bth&AN=121141170&site=eds-live>
12. Ibrahim, Halima. *Effect of External Public Debt on Economic Growth: an Empirical Analysis of East African Countries*. 2015;48.
13. Dey SR, Tareque M. External debt and growth: role of stable macroeconomic policies. *J Econ Financ Adm Sci*. 2020;25(50):185–204.
14. Anderu KS, Omolade A, Oguntuase A. External debt and economic growth in Nigeria. *J African Union Stud*. 2019;8(3):157–71.
15. Atinafu W. External debt-growth nexus: Empirical evidence from Ethiopian economy. *Econ Manag Sustain*. 2020;5(2):6–27.
16. Ehigiamusoe KU, Lean HH. The role of deficit and debt in financing growth in West Africa. *J Policy Model* [Internet]. 2020;42(1):216–34. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpolmod.2019.08.001>
17. Calderón C, Fuentes JR. *Government Debt and Economic Growth*. Inter-American Dev Bank. 2013;1–16.
18. Charles O. Domestic Debt and the Growth of Nigerian Economy. 2012;3(5):45–57.

19. Boboye AL, Ojo MO. Effect of External Debt on Economic Growth and Development of Nigeria. *Int J Bus Soc Sci.* 2012;3(12):297–304.
20. Anning L, Frimpong Ofori C, Kwame Affum E. The Impact of Government Debt on the Economic Growth of Ghana: A Time Series Analysis from 1990-2015. *Int J Innov Econ Dev.* 2015;2(5):31–9.
21. Were M. Impact of External Debt on Economic Growth in Kenya. *UNU World Inst Dev Econ Res Katajanokanlaituri 6 B, 00160 Helsinki, Finl.* 2001;17–8.
22. World Bank [Internet]. 2020. Available from: <https://www.worldbank.org>
23. OECD. Net ODA (indicator) [Internet]. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. 2022 [cited 2022 Mar 5]. p. 1. Available from: <https://data.oecd.org/oda/net-oda.htm>
24. Banerjee A, Juan J. D, John W. G, David H. Co-integration, Error Correction, and the Econometric Analysis of Non-Stationary Data. *Oxford Scholarship Online*; 1993.
25. Gujarati DN. Gujarati, D.N. 2004. *Basic Econometrics*. 4th ed. McGraw-Hil T, editor. New York: Gary Burke; 2004.
26. Okyere I. The Impact of Export and Import to Economic Growth of Ghana. *Eur J Bus Manag.* 2020;12(21):130–8.
27. Chemedda FE. THE ROLE OF EXPORTS IN ECONOMIC GROWTH WITH REFERENCE TO ETHIOPIAN COUNTRY. 2001;(May):17.
28. Ugochukwu US, Chinyere UP. The Impact of Capital Market on the Growth of the Nigerian Economy Under Democratic Rule. *Res J Financ Account.* 2013;4(9):53–62.
29. Pasara MT, Garidzirai R. Causality effects among gross capital formation, unemployment and economic growth in South Africa. *Economies.* 2020;8(2).
30. Forte R, Moura R. The effects of foreign direct investment on the host country's economic growth: Theory and empirical evidence. *Singapore Econ Rev.* 2013;58(3).
31. Adeleke KM, Olowe SO, Fasesin OO. Impact of Foreign Direct Investment on Nigeria Economic Growth. *Int J Acad Res Bus Soc Sci.* 2014;4(8):234–42.
32. Batikawai ER. An empirical analysis of the impact of official development assistance (ODA) on economic growth: evidence from Fiji. *Appl Econom Proj Pap.* 2020;(October):1–18.
33. Mallik G. Foreign Aid and Economic Growth: A Cointegration Analysis of the Six Poorest African Countries. *Econ Anal Policy* [Internet]. 2008;38(2):251–60. Available from: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0313-5926\(08\)50020-8](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0313-5926(08)50020-8)

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